

Preparation of data base for the determination and estimation of high explosives and a comparative study of different methods of estimation of RDX

S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri*

Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : sprasadsharma@rediffmail.com, sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 11 June 2007, revised 12 October 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : Analysis of post explosion residues containing high explosive and quick disposal of cases require a suitable analytical data base in the laboratory for the rapid detection and estimation of explosives in the residues. GC-MS is found to be appropriate for the separation, detection and estimation of explosives and a suitable data base for the detection and estimation of high explosives is presented. RDX has been found to be one of the main constituents of the explosives. Depending on the availability of RDX in the post explosion residues, suitable analytical method is needed for its detection and estimation. A comparative study of the different methods of detection and quantitation of RDX using UV-Vis, FTIR, GC-MS, HPLC and HPTLC instruments has been made for proper selection of the analytical method.

The range of detection and estimation of RDX is 100 μg – 1 ng or less depending on the method used.

Two chromogenic agents tryptophan and chromotropic acid used for the detection of CH_2O and RDX (which decompose to $3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ in presence of strong H_2SO_4) were examined for the quantitation of CH_2O and traces of RDX.

Formaldehyde in presence of H_2SO_4 and traces of FeCl_3 solution reacts with tryptophan to form a red colored complex with absorption maximum at 451 nm. Similarly, CH_2O (RDX) reacts with chromotropic acid in 16 N H_2SO_4 to form a blue-violet colored complex with an absorption maximum at 577 nm. However, CH_2O can be completely converted into the complex with large excess of tryptophan or chromotropic acid and the extinction coefficients of the complex are utilized for the quantitation of CH_2O or RDX. The stability constant of the complex at 298 K between CH_2O and chromotropic acid has been determined.

Keywords : CH_2O , chromotropic acid, FTIR, GC-MS, HPLC, HPTLC, RDX, tryptophan.

Introduction

Analysis of post explosion residues, traces of explosives on suspect's hands, on clothing and related matters, their detection and identification are of importance in forensic analysis. Usually explosives are collected with large amount of debris. Preliminary screening of the debris by visual and microscopic examinations, color tests, extractions, clean up procedures are to be done before final analysis.

The organic explosives and impurities are extracted by a suitable organic solvent like acetone and the impurities are removed by adsorption on a solid sorbent and elution of the explosives from the sorbent. Inorganic explosives and impurities are extracted by water. The techniques are well summarized in different books and the references cited therein¹⁻⁶. In most cases of forensic investigation, identification of the explosives and their decomposition products are important. Quantitation is necessary for the assay of the constituents of unexploded bombs or in other special circumstances.

Due to increasing demand of rapid investigating reports of explosive exhibits for juridical examinations, a suitable data base is necessary for the rapid disposal of cases.

The object of the present study is :

- (i) To prepare a data base for the separation, detection and estimation (if necessary) for rapid analysis of high explosive exhibits collected from the crime scene by different investigating agencies.
- (ii) To compare the different methods (Ultraviolet and visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) and gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) of identification and estimation of RDX using standard reference sample and unknown seized sample of black cake containing RDX.
- (iii) To determine the association constants between formaldehyde (CH_2O) and chromotropic acid in concentrated H_2SO_4 .

Retired Professor, Department of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Emiritus Fellow, AICTE, and Research Advisor, CFSL, Kolkata, India.

The results are reported in the present investigation.

Experimental

The standard samples of the explosives namely cyclonite (RDX), trinitrotoluene (TNT), pentaerithro-tol tetranitrate (PETN), *N*-methyl-2,4,6-tetranitroaniline (Tetryl), nitroglycerine (NG), octogen (HMX) were collected from High Energy Materials Research Laboratory, Pune and were used as such. CH₂O (A.R. grade, B.D.H.) utilized in the experiment was assayed titrimetrically in the way suggested in the literature⁷. Acetonitrile and benzene (HPLC grade, E. Merck, Germany), tryptophan (A.R., B.D.H., England), chromotropic acid (G.R., E. Merck, Germany) and H₂SO₄ (G.R., E. Merck, India) were used in the experiments. In general, the collected explosives are dissolved in a suitable organic solvent and the constituents are identified and estimated by GC-MS.

For rapid analysis of explosives, a mixture of known weight of explosive compounds (reference standards) namely RDX, TNT, PETN, Tetryl, NG, HMX was prepared by dissolving them in known volume of acetone. The mixture was allowed to pass through GC-MS where GC separates the compounds with their characteristics *R_t*

values. MS gives the spectra and TIC values of explosives and their characteristic *m/z* values. The results are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. The data (*R_t* and TIC) of the explosives of known concentration may be utilized for the rapid analysis of explosives present in the seized samples.

Spectrophotometric method (UV-visible) :

It is well known that CH₂O forms a violet blue colored complex with chromotropic acid⁸ in 16 *N* H₂SO₄ solution. RDX is decomposed in presence of concentrated H₂SO₄ to CH₂O which with chromotropic acid gives violet colored complex. RDX is usually detected by TLC using UV light and acidic solution of chromotropic acid, but the estimation of RDX was not done previously.

But quantitation of CH₂O and RDX is possible if CH₂O is completely converted to the blue complex with chromotropic acid with an absorption maximum at 577 nm (Fig. 3). When a known concentration of CH₂O in water was treated with increasing concentration of chromotropic acid in 16 *N* H₂SO₄, o.d. value at 577 nm of the complex gradually increased and became constant when chromotropic acid concentration was about 25 times greater than that of CH₂O. The development of color was

Fig. 1. A typical TIC and mass spectrum of the constituents of explosive sample.

F:\DATA\1Spsmix

04/25/0103.56.43

Fig. 2. A typical TIC and mass spectrum of the constituents of explosive sample.

Fig. 3. UV-Visible spectrum of the blue violet complex of chromotropic acid and formaldehyde.

good with 16 N H_2SO_4 but the color development was rapid with higher concentration of H_2SO_4 . Under this condition, CH_2O can be considered to be completely converted to blue complex and it was found that the complex obeyed Lambert-Beer's law at low concentrations. CH_2O , RDX and chromotropic acid do not show absorption in this region. Thus from o.d. value at 577 nm, extinction coefficient (ϵ) of the complex was determined. It was utilized for determining the percentage or concentration of RDX in the black cake or from any unknown sample in the way given below.

A definite quantity of the sample (here RDX in black cake) is treated with excess of chromotropic acid in presence of concentrated H_2SO_4 (16 N or more). From the o.d. reading and ϵ -value (17524) of the complex,

Fig. 4. UV-Visible spectrum of the blue violet complex of RDX and tryptophan.

concentration of percentage of RDX in black cake can be determined. The percentage concentration of RDX in black cake thus determined is given in Table 1 and the value compares well with the values determined by other techniques.

Table 1. Estimation of RDX in sample by UV-Visible

spectrophotometer after complex formation with chromotropic acid

Sl. no.	Concentration of RDX	Absorbance at 577 nm	Extinction coefficient (ε)	ε-Average	Concentration and % of RDX in black cake
1.	3.842×10^{-6}	0.067	17438		
2.	7.684×10^{-6}	0.133	17308	17524	
3.	1.536×10^{-5}	0.268	17447	s.d. =	82.2
4.	3.073×10^{-5}	0.550	17903	±225	
5.	4.610×10^{-5}	0.808	17527		
6.	Sample	0.503			

For the determination of the stability constant of the blue complex, CH_2O in water and chromotropic acid in 16 N H_2SO_4 were mixed in different proportions and diluted to 100 ml with addition of water. From the o.d. values of the colored solutions and ε-values (17524), the concentrations of the complex in the different solutions were determined to calculate the stability constant of the complex at 298 K (Table 2).

Detection and estimation of RDX using tryptophan⁹ :

It is also known that CH_2O forms a blue violet colored complex with tryptophan in presence of FeCl_3 and concentrated H_2SO_4 . The complex absorbs at 451.3 nm⁹.

The method was utilized for the detection and estimation of RDX. Definite concentrations of RDX in acetone were taken in beakers and evaporated to dryness. The residues were dissolved in known concentration of H_2SO_4 . The samples in H_2SO_4 were mixed with excess of tryptophan (about 200 times more than that of RDX) and a little but same amount of FeCl_3 solution in all cases. These were made up to the mark (100 ml). The absorption spectrum of the complex is given in Fig. 4. The o.d. of the complex at 451.3 was used to estimate RDX. The complex obeys Lambert-Beer's law at low concentrations of RDX. The extinction coefficient of the complex were determined to be 19537 for RDX (really three times to that of CH_2O) which enabled the determination of RDX in black cake. The percentage of RDX in black cake was found to be 82% (Table 3). Indole acetic acid can also be used for this purpose⁵.

The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Stability constant (K) of the formaldehyde and chromotropic acid complex at 298 K

Sl. no.	c_1	c_2	x	K	Average value of K and s.d.
1.	12.768×10^{-5}	6.06×10^{-5}	2.531×10^{-5}	2.482×10^9	
2.	6.341×10^{-5}	12.12×10^{-5}	4.351×10^{-5}	1.872×10^9	2.384×10^9
3.	12.768×10^{-5}	8.08×10^{-5}	3.328×10^{-5}	1.735×10^9	s.d. = ±0.601
4.	19.152×10^{-5}	12.12×10^{-5}	5.443×10^{-5}	2.608×10^9	
5.	22.768×10^{-5}	2.22×10^{-5}	1.196×10^{-5}	3.223×10^9	

Table 3. Estimation of RDX in sample by UV-Visible spectrophotometer after complex formation with tryptophan

Sl. no.	Concentration of RDX	Absorbance at 451 nm	Extinction coefficient (ε)	ε-Average	Concentration and % of RDX in black cake
1.	2.274×10^{-5}	0.451	19832		
2.	4.549×10^{-5}	0.890	19564	19537	
3.	5.685×10^{-5}	1.120	19700	s.d. =	78.9
4.	8.527×10^{-5}	1.644	19279	± 240	
5.	1.137×10^{-4}	2.196	19313		
6.	Sample	0.709			

The spectrophotometric measurements were made using Shimadzu UV-2550 model fitted with Peltier controlled thermo regulator bath.

FTIR, GC-MS, HPLC and HPTLC methods of detection and estimation of RDX :

Appropriate experimental solutions were prepared for detection and estimation of RDX. There are :

- (a) 0.02461 g standard RDX and 0.08468 g of black cake each dissolved in 10 ml of acetone for FTIR experiments.
- (b) 0.01512 g of RDX (standard) and 0.0889 g of black cake each dissolved in 100 ml of acetone for MS and HPLC experiments.
- (c) 0.00513 g standard RDX and 0.01221 g of black cake each dissolved in 100 ml of acetone for HPTLC experiments.

The solutions were appropriately diluted in acetone depending on requirements. Micro liter syringe was utilized so that concentrations used were in micrograms in all cases.

For FTIR measurements the sample solution in acetone was spotted on a blank KBr pellet by microliter syringe. The spot was dried by passing hot air. The pellets were placed under the microscope and focused to measure the spectrum between 4000–700 cm^{-1} using transmission mode. RDX gives characteristic absorption peak at 1590 cm^{-1} for asymmetric vibration. The detection and estimation of RDX in the black cake was made at 1590 cm^{-1} from FTIR measurements of absorption of standard solution of RDX of known concentrations and the experimental solutions. Measurements were made at 298 K. For measurement of FTIR spectrum in the solid state, Perkin-Elmer spectrum GX FTIR with autoimage microscope having MCT detector working at 77 K (liquid nitrogen temperature) was used.

GC-MS (EI⁺ mode)^{2,4-6} :

The detection and estimation of RDX were made using thermo Finnigan Trace GC and Trace MS system. The variable volume of the standard solutions and the experimental solutions were injected by autosampler using the following parameters :

Column : Capillary RTX-5MS, 15 m length, 0.32 mm ID, 0.25 μ film thickness. Oven temperature was programmed between 70–280 °C with 15 °C/min increment. The injector temperature and the interface temperature were 250 °C and 280 °C respectively. The system was run at constant flow mode of 1.2 ml/min. Helium was the carrier gas. MS parameters were : mode

EI⁺, source temperature 140 °C, energy 70 eV, source current 150 mA, Lens 1 = 5 V, Lens 2 = 110 V, mass range scanned 30–400 amu, $R_t = 10.08$ min.

The quantitation of RDX using HPLC was made by (Jasco Corporation) (with UV 975 intelligent detector, PU 980 intelligent HPLC Pump) system using at 250 mm X 4.6 mm ID, C18 column (5 μ m particle size). The mobile phase was acetonitrile : water (70 : 30) (HPLC grade) at a flow rate of 1 ml/min and the UV detector wavelength (λ) was 254 nm.

The solutions (both standard and experimental) were injected gradually from 1 μ g to 10 μ g in each case and the area of the peak in the chromatogram was measured after each addition. The results are given in Table 4. From the standard curve for concentration vs area of the peak of the chromatogram, the % RDX in the sample was determined. It is quite apparent that the linearity is maintained well upto 6.9072 μ g.

Table 4. Estimation of RDX in sample by HPLC method

Sl. no.	Amount of RDX injected (μ g)	Area	Amount of black cake injected (μ g)	Area	% of RDX in black cake
1.	0.1512	79556	0.088	38730	
2.	0.3024	157421	0.176	76335	
3.	0.4536	234553	0.264	113342	83.1%
4.	0.6048	310338	0.352	154024	(average
5.	0.7560	389892	0.440	185148	value from
6.	0.9072	450379	0.528	220118	the linear
7.	1.0548	450245	0.616	239699	zone)
8.	1.2096	606763	0.704	261526	
9.	1.3608	647774	0.792	276715	
10.	1.5120	692421	0.880	292070	

Estimation of RDX using HPTLC :

Quantitative estimation of explosives was also made using HPTLC. Desaga HPTLC system with CD 60 desitometer, E. Merck's pre-coated F_{254 nm} TLC plates of 20 cm x 20 cm x 0.25 mm dimension of 80–00 mesh were used.

The standard and experimental solutions were spotted by auto-sampler at 10 positions (each) on different plates keeping 15 mm margin at the bottom and 20 mm each at right and left side. Each spot was given by 3 μ L/cycle with a break of 5 s in between two cycles, spot size being 3 mm. The run was carried out up to 70 mm from spot.

The plates were developed in Camag developing chamber saturated with benzene : acetone (3 : 1) solvent system. The developed plates were scanned by densitometer using 254 nm light beam of 10 mm length and 0.2 mm width.

Representative Table 5 shows the area of the spots of standard RDX and the experimental solutions of different concentration from which the concentration of RDX in the experimental sample was estimated.

Table 5. Estimation of RDX in sample by HPTLC method

Sl. no.	Amount of RDX spotted (µg)	Area	Amount of black cake spotted (µg)	Area	% of RDX in black cake
1.	0.075	31.4	0.182	62.7	
2.	0.15	63.2	0.366	125.1	
3.	0.30	124.2	0.732	244.3	81.1%
4.	0.45	170.5	1.098	331.6	(average
5.	0.60	235.1	1.464	415.2	value
6.	0.75	271.6	1.830	493.0	in the
7.	0.90	321.7	2.196	584.2	linear
8.	1.5	420.6	7.320	1443.9	zone)
9.	3.0	746.6	14.64	2075.3	
10.	4.5	981.5	21.26	2230.7	
11.	6.0	1202.3	29.28	2629.3	

Results and discussion

Stability constant of CH₂O + chromotropic acid complex :

The reaction⁶ between RDX and H₂SO₄ can be written as

The presence of 10–15% water in H₂SO₄ enhances the reaction rate. The reaction between CH₂O and chromotropic acid is given by

where c_1 , c_2 and x represent initial concentrations of formaldehyde (A), chromotropic acid (B) and x was the concentration of complex formed.

The equilibrium constant K for the reaction (1), at 298 K can be written as

$$K = x/(c_1 - x)(c_2 - 2x)^2 \quad (3)$$

The ionic strength can be regarded to be constant as the species are uncharged and concentration of acid is 16 N H₂SO₄ though a slight fluctuation of acidity is expected. CH₂O and chromotropic acid did not absorb in the region of measurement, x can be determined from o.d values since ϵ was determined accurately (described before) K value of the complex were calculated and presented in Table 2. The average K value $2.348 (\pm 0.601) \times 10^9$ shows very high stability of the complex.

The composition of the complex formed between CH₂O, tryptophan, FeCl₃ and H₂SO₄ is not known with certainty but the extinction coefficient of the complex was determined (described before) which enabled both the detection and estimation of RDX in the unknown sample. The results are presented in Table 3.

Method utilizing IR spectra^{2,4,10} :

The O atoms of NO₂ group can be regarded to be equivalent due to resonance.

NO₂ group shows three characteristic vibrational frequencies in the region 1530–1560 cm⁻¹ (strong, asymmetric), symmetric frequency in the region 1210–1360 cm⁻¹ (strong) and bending frequency or scissoring in the region 840–930 cm⁻¹ (medium).

The absorption peak for asymmetric vibration at 1590 cm⁻¹ was taken for the estimation of RDX. This peak is conspicuously different from the characteristic asymmetric vibrational peaks of other nitro explosives viz. 1534.7 cm⁻¹ for TNT, 1645.3 cm⁻¹ for PETN, 1663.19 cm⁻¹ for nitroglycerine, 1658 cm⁻¹ for nitrocellulose etc. Table 6 shows the absorption or %T of RDX at different concentration and percentage of RDX in black cake. The absorption readings show a linear relationship with concentration which favours the estimation of RDX in unknown samples.

The method is easy, accurate but fairly high concentration of RDX is to be used for estimation.

Detection and estimation of RDX using GC-MS, HPLC and HPTLC^{2,5,10-14} :

RDX can be identified from R_f value of TIC (Figs. 1

and 2) and m/z values. In case of RDX, molecular ions are not observed from MS (EI^+) but the ions with m/z values 46 (NO_2), 30 (NO) were most abundant with 120 $[CH_2N(NO_2)_2]^+$, 148 $[CH_2N(NO_2)_2]^+$. Other peaks and the tentative species were 98 ($C_2H_2N_4O^+$), 83 ($CH_2NH_3O^+$) or $C_3N_3H_3^+$, 81 ($C_2HN_4^+$) or $C_3N_3H_3^+$, 75 ($CHNO_3^+$), 71 (CHN_3O^+), 56 ($(CH_2)_2N_2^+$), 42 ($(CH_2)_2N^+$ or CH_2N_2 .

Table 6. Estimation of RDX in sample by FTIR method

Sl. no.	Concentration of RDX	Absorbance at 1590 cm^{-1}	Extinction coefficient (ϵ)	ϵ -Average	Concentration % of RDX in black cake
1.	1.1085×10^{-3}	0.0131	12.08		
2.	2.2171×10^{-3}	0.0268	11.80		
3.	3.3256×10^{-3}	0.0401	12.05	11.89	3.133×10^{-3}
4.	4.4342×10^{-3}	0.0520	11.72	s.d. =	
5.	8.8684×10^{-3}	0.1038	11.80	± 0.163	82.27
6.	Sample	0.0376			

From the comparison of the R_t and TIC values of the standard solutions and the experimental solutions, % of RDX in the black cake can be determined.

For HPLC and HPTLC peak areas of the chromatograms were plotted against known concentrations of standard RDX solutions and the concentration of the unknown solution can be obtained from the linear portion of the calibration curve. Non linearity involves errors.

Conclusions :

The analysis of the explosives is mainly for forensic investigations. It is known that for forensic investigations :

- Only a minute amount (mixed with other ingredients and impurities) of sample is usually (not always) recovered from the crime scene.
- Sufficient amount of sample may not be available to repeat the experiment as crime can not be repeated.
- The results must be repeatable, reproducible and authenticated by more than one method.

Depending on the availability of the samples and instruments, suitable technique should be adopted. The results suggested that a very small quantity of RDX (1 ng or less) can be estimated by MS.

The detection limits are 10–50 ng for HPTLC, 50–100 ng for HPLC, 1–10 μg for spectrophotometry and about 100 μg for FTIR.

For ordinary purpose, RDX with chromotropic acid in presence of conc. H_2SO_4 are sufficiently reliable for the detection and estimation of RDX using TLC and a simple spectrophotometer. For minute amount of sample HPLC, HPTLC and GC-MS are useful. But if sufficient amount of sample is available, the non-destructive FTIR method may be utilized to preserve the sample as exhibits.

The methods are applicable to other explosive or explosive mixtures for juridical examination.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. M. S. Rao, Chief Forensic Scientist to the Govt. of India, for initiating the work. The authors also thank Dr. C. N. Bhattacharyya, Director, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata, for helping us in all possible ways to carry out the work and allowing laboratory facilities. One of the author (S.P.S.) expresses his indebtedness to his wife Mrs. Kakali Sharma for her constant encouragement and help in all possible ways.

References

- R. Saferstein, "Criminalistics", 7th ed., Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 2001, Chapter 11.
- B. McCord and E. C. Bander, in "Forensic Investigation of Explosions", ed. A. Beveridge, Chap. 8, S. Zitrin, Chap. 9, R. W. Hiley, Chap.10, Taylor and Francis Ltd., London, 1998.
- T. Urbanski, "Chemistry and Technology of Explosives", Pergamon Press, Oxford, UK, 1990, Vol. 3, p. 81.
- J. Yinon and S. Zitrin, "Modern Methods and Applications in Analysis of Explosives", John Wiley, Chichester, 1993, Chaps. 2 and 3.
- D. D. Fettero, in "Forensic Applications of Mass Spectrometry", ed. J. Yinon, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1995.
- J. Yinon, in "Hand Book of Analytical Separations", Vol. II, Forensic Science, ed. M. J. Bogusz, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2000, Chap. 17.
- "The British Pharmacopoeia 2000", printed in UK by Stationary Office Ltd. under the authority and superintendence of the Ccontroller of Her Majesty's Stationary Office and Queen's printer of acts of Parliament, 2000, pp. Vol. 1, pp. 725-726.
- F. Feigl and V. Anger, "Spot Test in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1966, 434.
- J. Chrastil and R. M. Reinhardt, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **58**, 2848.
- S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Energetic Materials*, 2005, **23**, 239.
- S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 131.
- I. S. Lurie and J. D. Willer (Jr.), "High Performance Liquid Chromatography in Forensic Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, Inc, New York, 1983, Chap. 7.
- D. K. Kuila, B. Mukhopadhyaya and S. C. Lahiri, *Forensic Science Communications FBI, USA* (October 2006, Vol. 8, No. 4).
- S. P. Sharma, B. C. Purkait and S. C. Lahiri, *Forensic Science International*, 2005, **152**, 235.